

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On Analytical Approach to Prognosis of Manufacturing of Voltage Divider Biasing Common Emitter Amplifier with Account Mismatch-Induced Stress – On Increasing of Density of Elements

E. L. Pankratov^{1,2}

¹Department of Mathematics, Nizhny Novgorod State University, 23 Gagarin Avenue, Nizhny Novgorod 603950, Russia, ²Department of Mathematics, Nizhny Novgorod State Technical University, 24 in Street, Nizhny Novgorod 603950, Russia

Received: 25-10-2018; Revised: 15-11-2018; Accepted: 30-01-2019

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce an approach for prognosis of manufacturing of voltage divider biasing common emitter amplifier based on bipolar transistors with account mismatch-induced stress. Based on this prognosis, we formulate some recommendations for optimization of manufacturing of the amplifier. Main aims of the optimization are as follows: (1) Decreasing dimensions of elements of the considered operational amplifier and (2) increasing of performance and reliability of the considered bipolar transistors. Dimensions of considered bipolar transistors will be decreased due to manufacture of these transistors framework heterostructure with specific structure, doping of required areas of the heterostructure by diffusion or ion implantation, and optimization of annealing of dopant and/or radiation defects. Performance and reliability of the above bipolar transistors could be increased by optimization of annealing of dopant and/or radiation defects and using inhomogeneity of the properties of heterostructure. Choosing of inhomogeneity properties of heterostructure leads to increasing of compactness of distribution of concentration of dopant. At the same time, one can obtain increasing of homogeneity of the above concentration. In this paper, we also introduce an analytical approach for prognosis of technological process of manufacturing of the considered operational amplifier. The approach gives a possibility to take into account variation of parameters of processes in space and at the same time in space. At the same time, one can take into account nonlinearity of the considered processes.

Key words: Voltage divider biasing common emitter amplifier, increasing integration rate of bipolar transistors, optimization of manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

In the present time, several actual problems of the solid-state electronics (such as increasing of performance, reliability, and density of elements of integrated circuits: Diodes, and field effect and bipolar transistors) are intensively solving.^[1-6] To increase the performance of these devices, it is attracted an interest determination of materials with higher values of charge carriers mobility.^[7-10] One way to decrease dimensions of the elements of integrated circuits is manufacturing them in thin-film heterostructures.^[3-5,11] In this case, it is possible to use inhomogeneity of heterostructure and necessary optimization of doping of electronic materials^[12,13] and development of epitaxial technology to improve these materials (including analysis of mismatch induced stress).^[14-16] An alternative approaches to increase dimensions of integrated circuits are using of laser and microwave types of annealing.^[17-19] Framework the paper, we introduce an approach to manufacture a bipolar transistor. The approach gives a possibility to dimensions of the transistor framework a voltage divider biasing common

Address for correspondence:

E. L. Pankratov,
E-mail: elp2004@mail.ru

emitter amplifier. We also consider possibility to decrease mismatch-induced stress to decrease quantity of defects, generated due to the stress. In this paper, we consider a heterostructure, which consists of a substrate and an epitaxial layer [Figure 1]. We also consider a buffer layer between the substrate and the epitaxial layer. The epitaxial layer includes into itself several sections, which were manufactured using another material. These sections have been doped by diffusion or ion implantation to manufacture the required types of conductivity (p or n). These areas became sources, drains, and gates [Figure 1]. After this doping, it is required annealing of dopant and/or radiation defects. Main aim of the present paper is the analysis of redistribution of dopant and radiation defects to determine conditions, which corresponds to decrease of the elements of the considered divider and at the same time to increase their density. At the same time, we consider a possibility to decrease mismatch-induced stress.

METHOD OF SOLUTION

To solve our aim, we determine and analyzed spatiotemporal distribution of the concentration of dopant in the considered heterostructure. We determine the distribution by solving the second Fick's law in the following form.^[1,20-24]

$$\frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_s}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} C(x, y, W, t) dW \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_s}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} C(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: (a) Structure of the considered voltage divider.^[13] (b) Heterostructure with a substrate, epitaxial layers, and buffer layer (view from side)

With boundary and initial conditions,

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L_x} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = 0, C(x, y, z, 0) = f_C(x, y, z), \\ \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{x=L_y} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{x=L_z} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $C(x, y, z, t)$ is the spatiotemporal distribution of concentration of dopant; Ω is the atomic volume of dopant; ∇_s is the symbol of surficial gradient; $\int_0^{L_z} C(x, y, z, t) dz$ is the surficial concentration of dopant on interface between layers of heterostructure (in this situation, we assume that Z-axis is perpendicular to interface between layers of heterostructure); $\mu_1(x, y, z, t)$ is the chemical potential due to the presence of mismatch-induced stress; and D and D_s are the coefficients of volumetric and surficial diffusions. Values of dopant diffusions coefficients depend on properties of materials of heterostructure, speed of heating and cooling of materials during annealing, and spatiotemporal distribution of concentration of dopant. Dependences of dopant diffusions coefficients on parameters could be approximated by the following relations.^[22-24]

$$\begin{aligned} D_C = D_L(x, y, z, T) \left[1 + \xi \frac{C^\gamma(x, y, z, t)}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right] \left[1 + \zeta_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, t)}{V^*} + \zeta_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, t)}{(V^*)^2} \right], \\ D_S = D_{SL}(x, y, z, T) \left[1 + \xi_S \frac{C^\gamma(x, y, z, t)}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right] \left[1 + \zeta_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, t)}{V^*} + \zeta_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, t)}{(V^*)^2} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, $D_L(x, y, z, T)$ and $D_{SL}(x, y, z, T)$ are the spatial (due to accounting all layers of heterostructure) and temperature (due to Arrhenius law) dependences of dopant diffusion coefficients; T is the temperature of annealing; $P(x, y, z, T)$ is the limit of solubility of dopant; parameter γ depends on properties of materials and could be integer in the following interval $\gamma \in [1, 3, 22]$ $V(x, y, z, t)$ is the spatiotemporal distribution of concentration of radiation vacancies; V^* is the equilibrium distribution of vacancies. Concentration dependence of dopant diffusion coefficient has been described in details in.^[22] Spatiotemporal distributions of the concentration of point radiation defects have been determined by solving the following system of equations.^[20,23,24]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\ + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] - k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, t) - k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) \\ \times I(x, y, z, t) V(x, y, z, t) + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\ + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_V(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_V(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right] \\ &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_V(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right] - k_{V,V}(x,y,z,T) V^2(x,y,z,t) - k_{I,V}(x,y,z,T) \\ &\times I(x,y,z,t) V(x,y,z,t) + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_s (x,y,z,t) \int_0^{L_z} V(x,y,W,t) dW \right] \\ &\times \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_s (x,y,z,t) \int_0^{L_z} V(x,y,W,t) dW \right] \end{aligned}$$

With boundary and initial conditions,

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L_x} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} \\ &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=L_y} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L_z} \\ &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L_x} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} \\ &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=L_y} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial V(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L_z} \\ &= 0, I(x,y,z,0) = f_I(x,y,z), V(x,y,z,0) = f_V(x,y,z). \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Here, $I(x,y,z,t)$ is the spatiotemporal distribution of concentration of radiation interstitials; I^* is the equilibrium distribution of interstitials; $D_I(x,y,z,T)$, $D_V(x,y,z,T)$, $D_{IS}(x,y,z,T)$, and $D_{VS}(x,y,z,T)$ are the coefficients of volumetric and surficial diffusions of interstitials and vacancies, respectively; terms $V^2(x,y,z,t)$ and $I^2(x,y,z,t)$ correspond to generation of divacancies and di-interstitials, respectively (for example, [24] and appropriate references in this book); and $k_{I,V}(x,y,z,T)$, $k_{I,I}(x,y,z,T)$, and $k_{V,V}(x,y,z,T)$ are the parameters of recombination of point radiation defects and generation of their complexes.

Spatiotemporal distributions of divacancies $\Phi_V(x,y,z,t)$ and di-interstitials $\Phi_I(x,y,z,t)$ could be determined by solving the following system of equations. [20,23,24]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right] \\ &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x,y,z,T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I,S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x,y,z,t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_I(x,y,W,t) dW \right] \\ &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I,S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x,y,z,t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_I(x,y,W,t) dW \right] + k_{I,I}(x,y,z,T) I^2(x,y,z,t) \\ &+ k_I(x,y,z,T) I(x,y,z,t) \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\ &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_V(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\ &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_V(x, y, W, t) dW \right] + k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, t) \\ &+ k_V(x, y, z, T) V(x, y, z, t) \end{aligned}$$

With boundary and initial conditions,

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L_x} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} \\ &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=L_y} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L_z} \\ &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L_x} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = 0, \\ \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=L_y} &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \left. \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L_z} = 0, \\ \Phi_I(x, y, z, 0) &= f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z), \Phi_V(x, y, z, 0) = f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here, $D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T)$, $D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T)$, $D_{\Phi_{IS}}(x, y, z, T)$, and $D_{\Phi_{VS}}(x, y, z, T)$ are the coefficients of volumetric and surficial diffusions of complexes of radiation defects; $k_I(x, y, z, T)$ and $k_V(x, y, z, T)$ are the parameters of decay of complexes of radiation defects.

Chemical potential μ_1 in Equation (1) could be determined by the following relation: ^[20]

$$\mu_1 = E(z) \Omega \sigma_{ij} [u_{ij}(x, y, z, t) + u_{ji}(x, y, z, t)] / 2, \tag{7}$$

Where, $E(z)$ is the Young modulus, σ_{ij} is the stress tensor; $u_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$ is the deformation tensor; u_i, u_j are the components $u_x(x, y, z, t)$, $u_y(x, y, z, t)$, and $u_z(x, y, z, t)$ of the displacement vector $\vec{u}(x, y, z, t)$; and x_i, x_j are the coordinate x, y, z . The Equation (3) could be transformed to the following form.

$$\begin{aligned} (x, y, z, t) &= \left[\frac{\partial u_i(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_i} \right] \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u_i(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_i} \right] \right. \\ &\left. - \varepsilon_0 \delta_{ij} + \frac{\sigma(z) \delta_{ij}}{1 - 2\sigma(z)} \left[\frac{\partial u_k(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_k} - 3\varepsilon_0 \right] - K(z) \beta(z) [T(x, y, z, t) - T_0] \delta_{ij} \right\} \frac{\Omega}{2} E(z), \end{aligned}$$

Where, σ is Poisson coefficient; $\varepsilon_0 = (a_s - a_{EL}) / a_{EL}$ is the mismatch parameter; a_s, a_{EL} are lattice distances of the substrate and the epitaxial layer; K is the modulus of uniform compression; β is the coefficient of thermal expansion; and T_r is the equilibrium temperature, which coincides (for our case) with room

temperature. Components of displacement vector could be obtained by solution of the following equations.^[25]

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xz}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \\ \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{\partial \sigma_{yx}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yz}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \\ \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{\partial \sigma_{zx}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{zy}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{zz}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \end{aligned} \right.$$

Where, $\sigma_{ij} = \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial u_i(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{3} \frac{\partial u_k(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_k} \right] + K(z) \delta_{ij} \times \frac{\partial u_k(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_k} - \times \frac{\partial u_k(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x_k} - \beta(z) K(z) [T(x, y, z, t) - T_r] \rho(z)$ is the density of materials of heterostructure, and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol. With account, the relation for σ_{ij} last system of equation could be written as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \left\{ K(z) + \frac{5E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2 u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \\ &\times \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z^2} \right] + \left[K(z) + \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right] \\ &\times \frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial z} - K(z) \beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial y} \right] - \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \\ &\times K(z) \beta(z) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \right\} + \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y^2} \\ &\times \left\{ \frac{5E(z)}{12[1+\sigma(z)]} + K(z) \right\} + \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y \partial z} + K(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial y} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial z} \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{\partial^2 u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y \partial z} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ K(z) \left[\frac{\partial u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{1}{6} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{1 + \sigma(z)} \left[6 \frac{\partial u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial u_x(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_y(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u_z(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] \right\} \\
 & - K(z) \beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Conditions for the system of Equation (8) could be written in the form.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \bar{u}(0, y, z, t)}{\partial x} = 0; & \quad \frac{\partial \bar{u}(L_x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \bar{u}(x, 0, z, t)}{\partial y} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \bar{u}(x, L_y, z, t)}{\partial y} = 0; \\
 \frac{\partial \bar{u}(x, y, 0, t)}{\partial z} = 0; & \quad \frac{\partial \bar{u}(x, y, L_z, t)}{\partial z} = 0; \quad \bar{u}(x, y, z, 0) = \bar{u}_0; \quad \bar{u}(x, y, z, \infty) = \bar{u}_0.
 \end{aligned}$$

We determine spatiotemporal distributions of concentrations of dopant and radiation defects by solving the Equations (1), (3), and (5) framework standard method of averaging of function corrections.^[26] Previously, we transform the Equations (1), (3), and (5) to the following form with account initial distributions of the considered concentrations.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] \\
 & + f_c(x, y, z) \delta(t) + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_s}{kT} \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} C(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\
 & + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_s}{kT} \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} C(x, y, W, t) dW \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{1a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\
 & + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] - k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, t) \\
 & - k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) V(x, y, z, t) + f_I(x, y, z) \delta(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} V(x, y, W, t) dW \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +\Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] - k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, t) \\
 & - k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) V(x, y, z, t) + f_V(x, y, z) \delta(t) \\
 \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} & = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_I(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\
 & + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_I(x, y, W, t) dW \right] + k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) \\
 & + k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, t) + f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) \delta(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} & = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_V(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_V(x, y, W, t) dW \right] \\
 & + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} \Phi_V(x, y, W, t) dW \right] + k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) \\
 & + k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, t) + f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z) \delta(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Farther, we replace concentrations of dopant and radiation defects in the right sides of Equations (1a), (3a), and (5a) on their not yet known average values $\alpha_{1\rho}$. In this situation, we obtain equations for the first-order approximations of the required concentrations in the following form.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} & = \alpha_{1c} \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[z \frac{D_S}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] + \alpha_{1c} \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[z \frac{D_S}{kT} \nabla_s \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] \\
 & + f_C(x, y, z) \delta(t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1b}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} & = \alpha_{1I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, t) \right] + \alpha_{1I} \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[z \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, t) \right] \\
 & + f_I(x, y, z) \delta(t) - \alpha_{1I}^2 k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) - \alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V} k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3b}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \alpha_{1V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] + \alpha_{1V} \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[z \frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] \\ &+ f_V(x, y, z) \delta(t) - \alpha_{1V}^2 k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) - \alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V} k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) \\ \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \alpha_{1\Phi_I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] + \alpha_{1\Phi_I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] \\ &+ f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) \delta(t) + k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) + k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, t) \end{aligned} \tag{5b}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \alpha_{1\Phi_V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] + \alpha_{1\Phi_V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[\frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \right] \\ &+ f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z) \delta(t) + k_V(x, y, z, T) V(x, y, z, t) + k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, t). \end{aligned}$$

Integration of the left and right sides of the Equations (1b), (3b), and (5b) on time gives us possibility to obtain relations for above approximation in the final form.

$$\begin{aligned} C_1(x, y, z, t) &= \alpha_{1C} \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t D_{SL}(x, y, z, T) \frac{z}{kT} \left[1 + \varsigma_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, \tau)}{V^*} + \varsigma_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, \tau)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \\ &\times \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) \left[1 + \frac{\xi_S \alpha_{1C}^\gamma}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right] d\tau + \alpha_{1C} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t D_{SL}(x, y, z, T) \left[1 + \frac{\xi_S \alpha_{1C}^\gamma}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right] + \\ &\times \Omega \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) \frac{z}{kT} \left[1 + \varsigma_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, \tau)}{V^*} + \varsigma_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, \tau)}{(V^*)^2} \right] d\tau + f_C(x, y, z) \end{aligned} \tag{1c}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_1(x, y, z, t) &= \alpha_{1I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \alpha_{1I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \\ &+ f_I(x, y, z) - \alpha_{1I}^2 \int_0^t k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) d\tau - \alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V} \int_0^t k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) d\tau \end{aligned} \tag{3c}$$

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(x, y, z, t) &= \alpha_{1V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \alpha_{1V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \\ &+ f_V(x, y, z) - \alpha_{1V}^2 \int_0^t k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) d\tau - \alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V} \int_0^t k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) d\tau \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, t) &= \alpha_{1\Phi_I} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \\ &\times \alpha_{1\Phi_I} z + f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) + \int_0^t k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \tag{5c}$$

$$\Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, t) = \alpha_{1\Phi_V} z \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau$$

$$\times \alpha_{1\Phi_V} z + f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z) + \int_0^t k_{V'}(x, y, z, T) V(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_{V''}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau.$$

We determine average values of the first-order approximations of concentrations of dopant and radiation defects by the following standard relation.^[26]

$$\alpha_{1\rho} = \frac{1}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^\Theta \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} \rho_1(x, y, z, t) dz dy dx dt. \tag{9}$$

Substitution of the relations (1c), (3c). and (5c) into relation (9) gives us possibility to obtain required average values in the following form

$$\alpha_{1C} = \frac{1}{L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_C(x, y, z) dz dy dx, \alpha_{1I} = \sqrt{\frac{(a_3 + A)^2}{4a_4^2} - 4 \left(B + \frac{\Theta a_3 B + \Theta^2 L_x L_y L_z a_1}{a_4} \right)},$$

$$-\frac{a_3 + A}{4a_4}, \alpha_{1V} = \frac{1}{S_{IV00}} \left[\frac{\Theta}{\alpha_{1I}} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_I(x, y, z) dz dy dx - \alpha_{1I} S_{II00} - \Theta L_x L_y L_z \right],$$

Where, $S_{\rho\rho ij} = \int_0^\Theta (\Theta - t) \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} k_{\rho,\rho}(x, y, z, T) I_1^i(x, y, z, t) V_1^j(x, y, z, t) dz dy dx dt, a_4 = S_{II00}$

$$\times (S_{IV00}^2 - S_{II00} S_{VV00}), a_3 = S_{IV00} S_{II00} + S_{IV00}^2 - S_{II00} S_{VV00}, a_2 = \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_V(x, y, z) dz dy dx$$

$$\times S_{IV00} S_{IV00}^2 + S_{IV00} \Theta L_x^2 L_y^2 L_z^2 + 2 S_{VV00} S_{II00} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_I(x, y, z) dz dy dx - \Theta L_x^2 L_y^2 L_z^2 S_{VV00}$$

$$- S_{IV00}^2 \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_I(x, y, z) dz dy dx, a_1 = S_{IV00} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_I(x, y, z) dz dy dx, a_0 = S_{VV00}$$

$$\times \left[\int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_I(x, y, z) dz dy dx \right]^2, A = \sqrt{8y + \Theta^2 \frac{a_3^2}{a_4^2} - 4\Theta \frac{a_2}{a_4}}, B = \frac{\Theta a_2}{6a_4} + \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{q^2 + p^3} - q}$$

$$- \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{q^2 + p^3} + q}, q = \frac{\Theta^3 a_2}{24 a_4^2} \left(4a_0 - \Theta L_x L_y L_z \frac{a_1 a_3}{a_4} \right) - \Theta^2 \frac{a_0}{8 a_4^2} \left(4\Theta a_2 - \Theta^2 \frac{a_3^2}{a_4} \right)$$

$$- \frac{\Theta^3 a_2^3}{54 a_4^3} - L_x^2 L_y^2 L_z^2 \frac{\Theta^4 a_1^2}{8 a_4^2}, p = \Theta^2 \frac{4a_0 a_4 - \Theta L_x L_y L_z a_1 a_3}{12 a_4^2} - \frac{\Theta a_2}{18 a_4},$$

$$\alpha_{1\Phi_I} = \frac{R_{I1}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} + \frac{S_{II20}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} + \frac{1}{L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) dz dy dx$$

$$\alpha_{1\Phi_V} = \frac{R_{V1}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} + \frac{S_{VV20}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} + \frac{1}{L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z) dz dy dx,$$

Where, $R_{\rho_i} = \int_0^{\Theta} (\Theta - t) \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} k_I(x, y, z, T) I_1^i(x, y, z, t) dz dy dx dt.$

We determine approximations of the second and higher orders of concentrations of dopant and radiation defects framework standard iterative procedure of the method of averaging of function corrections.^[26] Framework this procedure to determine approximations of the n -th order of concentrations of dopant and radiation defects, we replace the required concentrations in the Equations (1c), (3c), and (5c) on the following sum $\alpha_{np} + \rho_{n-1}(x, y, z, t)$. The replacement leads to the following transformation of the appropriate equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C_2(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \left[1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, t)]^y}{P^y(x, y, z, T)} \right] \left[1 + \varsigma_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, t)}{V^*} + \varsigma_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, t)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \right. \\ &\times D_L(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \left. \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \left[1 + \varsigma_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, t)}{V^*} + \varsigma_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, t)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right. \\ &\times D_L(x, y, z, T) \left. \left\{ 1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, t)]^y}{P^y(x, y, z, T)} \right\} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \left[1 + \varsigma_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, t)}{V^*} + \varsigma_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, t)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \right. \\ &\times D_L(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \left. \left\{ 1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, t)]^y}{P^y(x, y, z, T)} \right\} \right\} + f_C(x, y, z) \delta(t) \\ &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \frac{D_S}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2C} + C(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} \\ &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \frac{D_S}{kT} \nabla_S \mu_1(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2C} + C(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{1d}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial I_2(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\ &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] - k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{1I} + I_1(x, y, z, t)]^2 - k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) \\ &\times [\alpha_{1I} + I_1(x, y, z, t)] [\alpha_{1V} + V_1(x, y, z, t)] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, W, t)] dW \right. \\ &\times \left. \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \right\} + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{3d}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial V_2(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] - k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{1V} + V_1(x, y, z, t)]^2 - k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) \\
 &\times [\alpha_{1I} + I_1(x, y, z, t)] [\alpha_{1V} + V_1(x, y, z, t)] + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, W, t)] dW \right. \\
 &\left. \times \frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \right\} + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} \\
 \frac{\partial \Phi_{2I}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_I} + \Phi_{1I}(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} + k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, t) \\
 &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \frac{D_{\Phi_I S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_I} + \Phi_{1I}(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} + k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, t) \\
 &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) \delta(t) \tag{5d}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial \Phi_{2V}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y} \right] \\
 &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left\{ \frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_V} + \Phi_{1V}(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} + k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, t) \\
 &+ \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left\{ \frac{D_{\Phi_V S}}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, t) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_V} + \Phi_{1V}(x, y, W, t)] dW \right\} + k_V(x, y, z, T) V(x, y, z, t) \\
 &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z} \right] + f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z) \delta(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Integration of the left and the right sides of Equations (1d), (3d), and (5d) gives us possibility to obtain relations for the required concentrations in the final form

$$C_2(x, y, z, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \left\{ 1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, \tau)]^\gamma}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right\} \left[1 + \zeta_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, \tau)}{V^*} + \zeta_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, \tau)}{(V^*)^2} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times D_L(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial x} d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t D_L(x, y, z, T) \left[1 + \zeta_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, \tau)}{V^*} + \zeta_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, \tau)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \\
 & \times \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial y} \left\{ 1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, \tau)]^\gamma}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t \left[1 + \zeta_1 \frac{V(x, y, z, \tau)}{V^*} + \zeta_2 \frac{V^2(x, y, z, \tau)}{(V^*)^2} \right] \\
 & \times D_L(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial C_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial z} \left\{ 1 + \xi \frac{[\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, z, \tau)]^\gamma}{P^\gamma(x, y, z, T)} \right\} d\tau + f_C(x, y, z) \\
 & + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \frac{D_S}{kT} \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \\
 & \times \Omega \frac{D_S}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2C} + C_1(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau \tag{1e}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2(x, y, z, t) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial x} d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial y} d\tau \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t D_I(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial I_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial z} d\tau - \int_0^t k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, z, \tau)]^2 d\tau \\
 & - \int_0^t k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, z, \tau)] [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, z, \tau)] d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \\
 & \times \Omega \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, W, \tau)] \\
 & \times \Omega \frac{D_{IS}}{kT} dW d\tau \tag{3e}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_2(x, y, z, t) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial x} d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial y} d\tau \\
 & + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t D_V(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial V_1(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial z} d\tau - \int_0^t k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, z, \tau)]^2 d\tau \\
 & - \int_0^t k_{I,V}(x, y, z, T) [\alpha_{2I} + I_1(x, y, z, \tau)] [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, z, \tau)] d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \nabla_S \mu(x, y, z, \tau)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \Omega \frac{D_{VS}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2V} + V_1(x, y, W, \tau)] \\
 & \times \Omega \frac{D_{VS}}{kT} dW d\tau + f_V(x, y, z) \\
 \Phi_{2I}(x, y, z, t) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial x} d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial y} \\
 & \times D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t D_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1I}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial z} d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \\
 & \times \frac{D_{\Phi_{IS}}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_I} + \Phi_{1I}(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_{IS}}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_I} + \Phi_{1I}(x, y, W, \tau)] dW \\
 & \times \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_{I,I}(x, y, z, T) I^2(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_I(x, y, z, T) I(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \\
 & + f_{\Phi_I}(x, y, z) \tag{5e}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_{2V}(x, y, z, t) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial x} d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial y} \\
 & \times D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) d\tau + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t D_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z, T) \frac{\partial \Phi_{1V}(x, y, z, \tau)}{\partial z} d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, \tau) \\
 & \times \frac{D_{\Phi_{VS}}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_V} + \Phi_{1V}(x, y, W, \tau)] dW d\tau + \Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \frac{D_{\Phi_{VS}}}{kT} \int_0^{L_z} [\alpha_{2\Phi_V} + \Phi_{1V}(x, y, W, \tau)] dW \\
 & \times \nabla_s \mu(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_{V,V}(x, y, z, T) V^2(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau + \int_0^t k_V(x, y, z, T) V(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau \\
 & + f_{\Phi_V}(x, y, z).
 \end{aligned}$$

Average values of the second-order approximations of required approximations using the following standard relation.^[26]

$$\alpha_{2\rho} = \frac{1}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^{\Theta} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} [\rho_2(x, y, z, t) - \rho_1(x, y, z, t)] dz dy dx dt. \tag{10}$$

Substitution of the relations (1e), (3e), and (5e) into relation (10) gives us possibility to obtain relations for required average values $a_{2\rho}$

$$a_{2C} = 0, a_{2\Phi_I} = 0, a_{2\Phi_V} = 0, \alpha_{2V} = \sqrt{\frac{(b_3 + E)^2}{4b_4^2} - 4 \left(F + \frac{\Theta a_3 F + \Theta^2 L_x L_y L_z b_1}{b_4} \right)} - \frac{b_3 + E}{4b_4},$$

$$\alpha_{2I} = \frac{C_V - \alpha_{2V}^2 S_{VV00} - \alpha_{2V} (2S_{VV01} + S_{IV10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}}{S_{IV01} + \alpha_{2V} S_{IV00}},$$

Where, $b_4 = \frac{1}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} S_{IV00}^2 S_{VV00} - \frac{1}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} S_{VV00}^2 S_{II00}$, $b_3 = -\frac{S_{II00} S_{VV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (2S_{VV01} + S_{IV10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) + \frac{S_{IV00} S_{VV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (S_{IV01} + 2S_{II10} + S_{IV01} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) + \frac{S_{IV00}^2}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (2S_{VV01} + S_{IV10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) - \frac{S_{IV00}^2 S_{IV10}}{\Theta^3 L_x^3 L_y^3 L_z^3}$, $b_2 = \frac{S_{II00} S_{VV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (S_{VV02} + S_{IV11} + C_V) - (S_{IV10} - 2S_{VV01} + \Theta L_x L_y \times L_z)^2 + \frac{S_{IV01} S_{VV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (\Theta L_x L_y L_z + 2S_{II10} + S_{IV01}) + \frac{S_{IV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (S_{IV01} + 2S_{II10} + 2S_{IV01} + \Theta L_x L_y \times L_z) (2S_{VV01} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z + S_{IV10}) - \frac{S_{IV00}^2}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (C_V - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}) + \frac{C_I S_{IV00}^2}{\Theta^2 L_x^2 L_y^2 L_z^2} - \frac{2S_{IV10}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} \times S_{IV00} S_{IV01}$, $b_1 = S_{II00} \frac{S_{IV11} + S_{VV02} + C_V}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (2S_{VV01} + S_{IV10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) + \frac{S_{IV01}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (\Theta L_x L_y \times L_z + 2S_{II10} + S_{IV01}) (2S_{VV01} + S_{IV10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) - \frac{S_{IV10} S_{IV01}^2}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} - \frac{S_{IV00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (3S_{IV01} + 2S_{II10} + \Theta L_x L_y L_z) (C_V - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}) + 2C_I S_{IV00} S_{IV01}$, $b_0 = \frac{S_{II00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} (S_{IV00} + S_{VV02})^2 - \frac{S_{IV01}}{L_x L_y L_z} \times \frac{1}{\Theta} (\Theta L_x L_y L_z + 2S_{II10} + S_{IV01}) (C_V - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}) + 2C_I S_{IV01}^2 - S_{IV01} \frac{C_V - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} \times \frac{1}{\Theta} (\Theta L_x L_y L_z + 2S_{II10} + S_{IV01})$, $C_I = \frac{\alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} S_{IV00} + \frac{\alpha_{1I}^2 S_{II00}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} - \frac{S_{II20} S_{II20}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z} - \frac{S_{IV11}}{\Theta L_x L_y L_z}$

$$C_V = \alpha_{1I} \alpha_{1V} S_{IV00} + \alpha_{1V}^2 S_{VV00} - S_{VV02} - S_{IV11}, E = \sqrt{8y + \Theta^2 \frac{a_3^2}{a_4^2} - 4\Theta \frac{a_2}{a_4}}, F = \frac{\Theta a_2}{6a_4}$$

$$+ \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{r^2 + s^3} - r} - \sqrt[3]{\sqrt{r^2 + s^3} + r}, r = \frac{\Theta^3 b_2}{24b_4^2} \left(4b_0 - \Theta L_x L_y L_z \frac{b_1 b_3}{b_4} \right) - \frac{\Theta^3 b_2^3}{54b_4^3} - b_0 \frac{\Theta^2}{8b_4^2}$$

$$\times \left(4\Theta b_2 - \Theta^2 \frac{b_3^2}{b_4} \right) - L_x^2 L_y^2 L_z^2 \frac{\Theta^4 b_1^2}{8b_4^2}, s = \Theta^2 \frac{4b_0 b_4 - \Theta L_x L_y L_z b_1 b_3}{12b_4^2} - \frac{\Theta b_2}{18b_4}.$$

Farther, we determine solutions of Equations (8), i.e., components of displacement vector. To determine the first-order approximations of the considered components framework method of averaging of function

corrections, we replace the required functions in the right sides of the equations by their not yet known average values a_i . The substitution leads to the following result.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{1x}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} &= -K(z) \beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x}, \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} \\ &= -K(z) \beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y}, \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{1z}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} = -K(z) \beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z}. \end{aligned}$$

Integration of the left and the right sides of the above relations on time t leads to the following result.

$$u_{1x}(x, y, z, t) = u_{0x} + K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta$$

$$-K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta,$$

$$u_{1y}(x, y, z, t) = u_{0y} + K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta$$

$$-K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta,$$

$$u_{1z}(x, y, z, t) = u_{0z} + K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta$$

$$-K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta.$$

Approximations of the second and higher orders of components of displacement vector could be determined using standard replacement of the required components on the following sums $a_i + u_i(x, y, z, t)$.^[26] The replacement leads to the following result.

$$\rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{2x}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} = \left\{ K(z) + \frac{5E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2 u_{1x}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\}$$

$$\times \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1z}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z^2} \right] - \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x}$$

$$\times K(z) \beta(z) + \left\{ K(z) + \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2 u_{1z}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial z}$$

$$\rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{2y}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t^2} = \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1x}(x, y, z, t)}{\partial x \partial y} \right] - \frac{\partial T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial y}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \times K(z)\beta(z) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} \right] \right\} + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y^2} \\ & \times \left\{ \frac{5E(z)}{12[1+\sigma(z)]} + K(z) \right\} + \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y \partial z} + K(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x \partial y} \\ \rho(z) \frac{\partial^2 u_{2z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2 u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1x}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x \partial z} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\partial^2 u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y \partial z} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ K(z) \left[\frac{\partial u_{1x}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_{1x}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right] \right\} \\ & + \frac{E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[6 \frac{\partial u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial u_{1x}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right] \\ & \left. - \frac{\partial u_{1x}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_{1y}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u_{1z}(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right] \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{1+\sigma(z)} - K(z)\beta(z) \frac{\partial T(x,y,z,t)}{\partial z} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Integration of the left and right sides of the above relations on time t leads to the following result.

$$\begin{aligned} u_{2x}(x,y,z,t) &= \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ K(z) + \frac{5E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ K(z) \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{E(z)}{2\rho(z)} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \frac{1}{1+\sigma(z)} + \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial z} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \left\{ K(z) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} - K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta T(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \\ & \times \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ K(z) + \frac{5E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} - \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \\ & \times \frac{1}{\rho(z)} - \frac{E(z)}{2\rho(z)[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \\ & - \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ K(z) + \frac{E(z)}{3[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta + u_{0x} + K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \\ & \times \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta T(x,y,z,\tau) d\tau d\vartheta \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{2y}(x, y, z, t) = & \frac{E(z)}{2\rho(z)} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \\
 & \times \frac{1}{1+\sigma(z)} + \frac{K(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ \frac{5E(z)}{12[1+\sigma(z)]} + K(z) \right\} \\
 & \times \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{1}{2\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{1+\sigma(z)} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \right\} - K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right. \\
 & \left. - K(z) \right\} \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y \partial z} \int_0^t \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{E(z)}{2\rho(z)} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \frac{1}{1+\sigma(z)} - K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{K(z)}{\rho(z)} \\
 & \times \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \left\{ \frac{5E(z)}{12[1+\sigma(z)]} \right. \\
 & \left. + K(z) \right\} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{1+\sigma(z)} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \right\} \\
 & \times \frac{1}{2\rho(z)} - \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \left\{ K(z) - \frac{E(z)}{6[1+\sigma(z)]} \right\} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y \partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + u_{0y} \\
 u_z(x, y, z, t) = & \frac{E(z)}{2[1+\sigma(z)]} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y \partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \frac{1}{\rho(z)} + \frac{1}{\rho(z)} \\
 & \times \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ K(z) \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right] \right\} + \frac{1}{6\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \frac{E(z)}{1+\sigma(z)} \left[6 \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 &-\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_0^\vartheta \int_0^\vartheta u_{1x}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \int_0^\vartheta \int_0^\vartheta u_{1y}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\vartheta \int_0^\vartheta u_{1z}(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta \right\} \\
 &-K(z) \frac{\beta(z)}{\rho(z)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \int_0^\vartheta \int_0^\vartheta T(x, y, z, \tau) d\tau d\vartheta + u_{0z}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Framework this paper, we determine concentration of dopant, concentrations of radiation defects, and components of displacement vector using the second-order approximation framework method of averaging of function corrections. This approximation is usually enough good approximation to make qualitative analysis and to obtain some quantitative results. All obtained results have been checked by comparison with results of numerical simulations.

DISCUSSION

In this section, we analyzed dynamics of redistributions of dopant and radiation defects during annealing and under influence of mismatch-induced stress. Typical distributions of concentrations of dopant in heterostructures are presented in Figures 2 and 3 for diffusion and ion types of doping, respectively. These distributions have been calculated for the case when value of dopant diffusion coefficient in the epitaxial layer is larger than in the substrate. The figures show that inhomogeneity of heterostructure gives us possibility to increase compactness of transistors. At the same time, one can find increasing homogeneity of dopant distribution in doped part of epitaxial layer. Increasing of compactness of transistors gives us possibility to increase their density.

The second effect leads to decrease local heating of materials during functioning of transistors or decreasing of their dimensions for fixed maximal value of local overheat. However, this framework approach of manufacturing of bipolar transistor, it is necessary to optimize annealing of dopant and/or radiation defects. If annealing time is small, the dopant did not achieve any interfaces between materials of heterostructure. In this situation, one cannot find any modifications of distribution of concentration of dopant. If annealing time is large, distribution of the concentration of dopant is too homogenous. We optimize annealing time framework recently introduces approach.^[15,25-32] Framework this criterion,

Figure 2: Distributions of the concentration of infused dopant in heterostructure from Figure 1 in direction, which is perpendicular to interface between epitaxial layer substrate. Increasing of number of curve corresponds to increase of difference between values of dopant diffusion coefficient in layers of heterostructure under condition when value of dopant diffusion coefficient in epitaxial layer is larger than the value of dopant diffusion coefficient in substrate

we approximate real distribution of concentration of dopant by step-wise function [Figures 4 and 5]. Farther, we determine optimal values of annealing time by minimization of the following mean-squared error.

$$U = \frac{1}{L_x L_y L_z} \int_0^{L_x} \int_0^{L_y} \int_0^{L_z} [C(x, y, z, \Theta) - \psi(x, y, z)]^2 dz dy dx, \tag{15}$$

Figure 3: Distributions of concentration of implanted dopant in heterostructure from Figure 1 in direction, which is perpendicular to interface between epitaxial layer substrate. Curves 1 and 3 correspond to annealing time $\Theta = 0.0048(L_x^2 + L_y^2 + L_z^2)/D_0$. Curves 2 and 4 correspond to annealing time $\Theta = 0.0057(L_x^2 + L_y^2 + L_z^2)/D_0$. Curves 1 and 2 correspond to homogenous sample. Curves 3 and 4 correspond to heterostructure under condition when value of dopant diffusion coefficient in epitaxial layer is larger than the value of dopant diffusion coefficient in substrate

Figure 4: Spatial distributions of dopant in heterostructure after dopant infusion. Curve 1 is idealized distribution of dopant. Curves 2–4 are real distributions of dopant for different values of annealing time. Increasing of number of curve corresponds to increase of annealing time

Where, $\psi(x,y,z)$ is the approximation function. Dependences of optimal values of annealing time on parameters are presented in Figures 6 and 7 for diffusion and ion types of doping, respectively. It should be noted that it is necessary to anneal radiation defects after ion implantation. One could find spreading of concentration of distribution of dopant during this annealing. In the ideal case, distribution of dopant achieves appropriate interfaces between materials of heterostructure during annealing of radiation

Figure 5: Spatial distributions of dopant in heterostructure after ion implantation. Curve 1 is idealized distribution of dopant. Curves 2–4 are real distributions of dopant for different values of annealing time. Increasing of number of curve corresponds to increase of annealing time

Figure 6: Dependences of dimensionless optimal annealing time for doping by diffusion, which have been obtained by minimization of mean-squared error, on several parameters. Curve 1 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on the relation a/L and $\xi = \gamma = 0$ for equal to each other values of dopant diffusion coefficient in all parts of heterostructure. Curve 2 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter ϵ for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\xi = \gamma = 0$. Curve 3 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter ξ for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\epsilon = \gamma = 0$. Curve 4 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter γ for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\epsilon = \xi = 0$

defects. If dopant did not achieve any interfaces during annealing of radiation defects, it is practically to additionally anneal the dopant. In this situation, optimal value of additional annealing time of implanted dopant is smaller than annealing time of infused dopant.

Farther, we analyzed the influence of relaxation of mechanical stress on distribution of dopant in doped areas of heterostructure. Under the following condition $\varepsilon_0 < 0$, one can find compression of distribution of concentration of dopant near interface between materials of heterostructure. Contrary (at $\varepsilon_0 > 0$) one can find spreading of distribution of the concentration of dopant in this area. This changing of distribution

Figure 7: Dependences of dimensionless optimal annealing time for doping by ion implantation, which have been obtained by minimization of mean-squared error, on several parameters. Curve 1 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on the relation a/L and $\xi = \gamma = 0$ for equal to each other values of dopant diffusion coefficient in all parts of heterostructure. Curve 2 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter ε for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\xi = \gamma = 0$. Curve 3 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter ξ for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\varepsilon = \gamma = 0$. Curve 4 is the dependence of dimensionless optimal annealing time on value of parameter γ for $a/L = 1/2$ and $\varepsilon = \xi = 0$

Figure 8: Normalized distributions of charge carrier mobility in the considered heterostructure. Curve 1 corresponds to the heterostructure, which has been considered in Figure 1. Curve 2 corresponds to a homogenous material with averaged parameters of heterostructure from Figure 1

Figure 9: Normalized dependences of component u_z of displacement vector on coordinate z for nonporous (curve 1) and porous (curve 2) epitaxial layers

of the concentration of dopant could be at least partially compensated using laser annealing.^[29] This type of annealing gives us possibility to accelerate diffusion of dopant and another process in annealed area due to inhomogeneous distribution of temperature and Arrhenius law Figure 8. Accounting relaxation of mismatch-induced stress in heterostructure could lead to change of optimal values of annealing time. Mismatch-induced stress could be used to increase density of elements of integrated circuits, on the other hand, could lead to generation dislocations of the discrepancy. Figure 9 shows distributions of the component of displacement vector, which is perpendicular to interface between layers of heterostructure.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we model redistribution of infused and implanted dopants with account relaxation mismatch-induced stress during manufacturing a bipolar heterotransistors framework a circuit of voltage divider biasing common emitter amplifier. We formulate recommendations for optimization of annealing to decrease dimensions of transistors and to increase their density. We formulate recommendations to decrease mismatch-induced stress. Analytical approach to model diffusion and ion types of doping with account concurrent changing of parameters in space and time has been introduced. At the same time, the approach gives us possibility to take into account non-linearity of considered processes.

REFERENCES

1. Lachin VI, Savelov NS. Electronics. Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix; 2001.
2. Polishcuk A. Mod Electron 2004;12:8.
3. Volovich G. Mod Electron 2006;2:10.
4. Kerentsev A, Lanin V. Power Electron 2008;1:34.
5. Ageev AO, Belyaev AE, Boltovets NS, Ivanov VN, Konakova RV, Kudrik YA, *et al.* Semiconductors 2009;43:897.
6. Tsai JH, Chiu SY, Lour WS, Guo DF. Semiconductors 2009;43:971.
7. Alexandrov OV, Zakhar'in AO, Sobolev NA, Shek EI, Makoviychuk MM, Parshin EO. Semiconductors 1998;32:1029.
8. Ermolovich IB, Milenin VV, Red'ko RA, Red'ko SM. Semiconductors 2009;43:1016.
9. Sinsersuksakul P, Hartman K, Kim SB, Heo J, Sun L, Park HH, *et al.* Enhancing the efficiency of SnS solar cells via band-offset engineering with a zinc oxysulfide buffer layer. Appl Phys Lett 2013;102:53901.
10. Reynolds JG, Reynolds CL, Mohanta A Jr., Muth JF, Rowe JE, Everitt HO, *et al.* Shallow acceptor complexes in p-type ZnO. Appl Phys Lett 2013;102:152114.

11. Volokobinskaya NI, Komarov IN, Matyukhina TV, Reshetnikov VI, Rush AA, Falina IV, *et al.* Semiconductors 2013;35:1013.
12. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. Doping of materials during manufacture p-n-junctions and bipolar transistors. analytical approaches to model technological approaches and ways of optimization of distributions of dopants. Rev Theor Sci 2013;1:58.
13. Chen X, Xue J, Xie SH, Huang W, Wang P, Gong K, *et al.* Error analysis of approximate calculation of voltage divider biased common-emitter amplifier. Circuits Syst 2017;8:247-52.
14. Kukushkin SA, Osipov AV, Romanychev AI. Epitaxial growth of zinc oxide by the method of atomic layer deposition on SiC/Si substrates. Phys Solid State 2016;58:1448-52.
15. Trukhanov EM, Kolesnikov AV, Loshkarev ID. Long-range stresses generated by misfit dislocations in epitaxial films. Russ Microelectron 2015;44:552-8.
16. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. On optimization of regimes of epitaxy from gas phase. Some analytical approaches to model physical processes in reactors for epitaxy from gas phase during growth films. Rev Theor Sci 2015;3:365-98.
17. Ong KK, Pey KL, Lee PS, Wee AT, Wang XC, Chong YF. Dopant distribution in the recrystallization transient at the maximum melt depth induced by laser annealing. Appl Phys Lett 2006;89:172111.
18. Wang HT, Tan LS, Chor EF. Pulsed laser annealing of Be-implanted GaN. J Appl Phys 2006;98:94901.
19. Bykov YV, Yermeev AG, Zharova NA, Plotnikov IV, Rybakov KI, Drozdov MN, *et al.* Diffusion processes in semiconductor structures during microwave annealing. Radiophys Quantum Electron 2003;43:836.
20. Zhang YW, Bower AF. Numerical simulations of island formation in a coherent strained epitaxial thin film system. J Mech Phys Solids 1999;47:2273-97.
21. Landau LD, Lefshits EM. Theoretical Physics, Theory of Elasticity. Vol. 7. Moscow: Physmatlit; 2001.
22. Gotra ZU. Technology of Microelectronic Devices. Moscow: Radio and Communication; 1991.
23. Fahey PM, Griffin PB, Plummer JD. Point defects and dopant diffusion in silicon. Rev Mod Phys 1989;61:289.
24. Vinetskiy VL, Kholodar GA. Radiative Physics of Semiconductors. Kiev: Naukova Dumka; 1979.
25. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. An approach to manufacture of bipolar transistors in thin film structures. On the method of optimization. Int J Micro-Nano Scale Transp 2014;4:17.
26. Sokolov YD. About the definition of dynamic forces in the mine lifting. Appl Mech 1955;1:23-35.
27. Pankratov EL. Dopant diffusion dynamics and optimal diffusion time as influenced by diffusion-coefficient nonuniformity. Russ Microelectron 2007;36:33-9.
28. Pankratov EL. Int J Nanosci 2008;7:187.
29. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. Decreasing of quantity of radiation defects in an im-plant-ed-junction rectifiers by using overlayers. Int J Micro-Nano Scale Transp 2012;3:119-30.
30. Pankratov EL. Nano 2011;6:31.
31. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. Application of radiation processing of materials to increase sharpness of p-n-junction in a semiconductor heterostructure. J Comp Theor Nanosci 2013;10:1888-94.
32. Pankratov EL, Bulaeva EA. On prognosis of technological process to optimize manufacturing of an invertors to increase density their of elements. J Nanoeng Nanomanuf 2016;6:313-26.